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Data Problems in the Humanities, or "When everybody is special, no one is"?

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That the humanities has ‘a data problem’ is now a common refrain amongst many communities. Humanists often argue that humanities data is a problem because they don’t have or work with data (Borgman, 2010; Posner, 2015). Librarians and information professionals, by contrast, believe that humanists have data, but assume they don’t realize it — meaning that the problem is that they must be trained to appropriately recognize and work with data they most surely have (Flanders, Julia, and Trevor Muñoz, 2012; Ikeshoji-Orlati, Caton, and Stringer-Hye, 2018). Digital humanists know that they (at least) have data, but believe that their data are special, distinct both from those used by scientists and (often) those “not recognized” by traditional humanists — and that these data require special strategies and techniques as a result (Drucker, 2011; Schöch, 2013). In a rough and general way each premise informs a mélange of assumptions, advice and best practices that comprise the emerging literature on research data management (RDM) in the humanities.

In this paper we argue that this focus on the discovery and definition of what is “special” about the definition or recognition of humanities data is a mistake. Humanities data are not special because of what they are, but rather because of how they are used (Borgman, 2017; Leonelli, 2015). Data are data, in other words, whether they are produced and used by scientists or humanists. The “problem” with Humanities data — and the thing that makes them special — lies in the use-case. Humanities data are both designed and structured by systems to meet scholarly or systematic ends. While many humanities researchers engage, as users, with desi-

gned research infrastructure, humanities scholars also innovate, design, and build scholar-led research infrastructure that have specific systems requirements, but often without clear requirements modeling. We draw out the implications of this argument on two fronts, looking at the issue of research, and the implications for humanities infrastructure development.

First, we report on the preliminary results of ongoing research examining how humanists think about data as they build, navigate, and utilize research infrastructure for scholarly purposes. Reported results derive from a series of comparative case studies (Eisenhardt, 1989; Maryl et al. 2020) examining four cases of scholar-led projects that deploy digital research infrastructure for scholarly ends. Cases were purposively selected using the following criteria: a. Are scholar-driven; b. Involve representation of ‘real world’ objects involving small, intensively curated datasets; c. Have a documented record of accomplishment and innovation.

Although humanists have a long history of designing and building research infrastructure, both analog and digital (Abbott, 2012; Bod, 2013) this has been less appreciated in the literature on humanities infrastructure design. By comparing elements from our case studies, we build on previous studies of humanists as both users of information resources (Bates, 1996a; 1996b; Bates et al. 1993; Buchanan, Gow, Blandford, Rimmer, and Warwick, 2006; Palmer, Teffeu, Pirmann, 2009; Stone, 1982; Rimmer, Warwick, Blandford, Gow, and Buchanan, G., 2008; Watson-Boone, 1994), and digital tools (Gibbs and Owens, 2022) to consider issues of use-case construction, both formally and informally, over time. Emphasizing the role of scholars as designers (Lamb and King, 2003; Millerand and Baker, 2010), we highlight the importance of the ‘use-case’ as a means to culturally frame and model system requirements, functional and non-functional, as a type of socio-technical fact, mediating between user-agency, the purpose of a scholarly project, and the design, development and maintenance of the research infrastructures innovated to meet those goals. Originating in software engineering, use-case modeling (Jacobson et al. 1992) is a means of specifying, validating, and eliciting system requirements, where use case models describe, communicate, and facilitate all of the ways a user interacting with a system or product may work to realize a desired end. While there is a robust literature on how to write and design use cases (Kulak, Daryl, and Guiney, 2012) there is little empirical study of use-case development or implementation in software engineering (Anda, 2003), and nothing that systematically examines the diffusion of the concept outside these arenas of expert work.

By comparing the roles of humanist researchers as designers, we complicate previous research on humanities work practices (Blanke and Hedges, 2013; Pachecho, 2022; Unsworth, 2000) and studies of interdisciplinary scholarly information practice more broadly (Palmer, 2013), drawing on the notion of ‘infrastructural practices’ (Baker and Millerand, 2016; Baker, Duerr, and Parsons, 2015; Edwards, 2019; Karasti and Blomberg, 2018) in scholarly information ecosystems (Altman and Cohen, 2022), and hence on the dual role of scholars as infrastructure designers-builders and users (Lamb and Kling, 2003; Millerand and Baer, 2010; Mongili, 2014).

While we acknowledge a few exceptions for specific tools and technical standards for the Digital Humanities (e.g. Voyant, TEI, IIF, CIDOC CRM), the Humanities generally lack the proliferation of a robust, distributed, yet centrally networked, ecosystem supporting generalizable infrastructure development process, linking standards with the infrastructure practices central to scholar originated infrastructure projects (c.f. Bosman and Kramer, 2015). Rather, humanities researchers have worked far more improvisationally (Ciula, 2022), and in the absence of a systematic

orientation to project requirements, have instead created custom knowledge infrastructure. As a result, the identification of discipline-wide standards for tools and infrastructure is far more difficult.

From the perspective of infrastructure design, development, and maintenance, therefore, the “problem of Humanities data” is how to support and interface with scholarly use-cases, the scenarios and problem sets scholars are concerned with, and engage with the custom infrastructural strategies they have developed to speak to them. In our conclusion, we point to some ways where a focus on use case modeling and system requirements planning can complement efforts to refine project development, particularly with reference to recent work on ‘data communities’ (Cooper and Springer, 2023) and community-oriented frameworks (Lyon, et. al 2012; Jeng and Oh, 2016; Jeng and He, 2022) to bring researchers and infrastructural partners into structured dialogue regarding requirements development.

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Data Remediation as Collaborative Process

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The Linked Infrastructure for Networked Cultural Scholarship (LINCS) is mobilizing Canadian scholarship through the creation, dissemination, and use of linked open data (LOD). The project goal is to allow users from fields including history, communications, music, performance, and literary studies to interweave their research material meaningfully with data from cultural data publishers (galleries, museums, archives, libraries, presses) in order to transform how it is possible to engage with culture on the Semantic Web. As the project prepares to launch in 2023, this paper reflects on the activities of core LINCS project members as forms of remediation. Not only does the project work towards what may provocatively be understood as “[t]he action of remedying or correcting” (OED) a variety of differently formatted datasets into a findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) state (Wilkison et al), but the results of this reworking allow for researchers and the public to remediate their knowledge through new methods of connection, visualization, and annotation.

This paper will reflect on three instances of dataset remediation within LINCS, using this term as a keyword for exploring the possibilities of LOD for the humanities, drawing on various senses of remediation from ecology (Shepherd), media studies (Bolter and

Grusin), and digital humanities (Schuster and Dunn), and on the concept of (meta)data remediation (Groat; Radio and Hanrath). We demonstrate how a dataset enters the LINCS conversion workflow, becomes a part of the LINCS triplestore, and is then accessed by researchers through a variety of interfaces. The remediation of these diverse source datasets, on advertisements, paintings, and literary history, will demonstrate the ways in which these three processes of remediation are crucial to the creation of LOD through LINCS, and to the improvement of the data environment or ecosystem.

The first process occurs before any data is exchanged: the remediation of research conceptualization. The LINCS Research Board Chair, Ontologist, Project Manager, and Data Interface Developer meet with the leads of each research project for a data intake interview. During these conversations, researchers often comment that questions from the LINCS team about intent, granularity, audience, difference, and provenance change the way they conceptualize their projects. Although this result is unintentional, eliciting the context that is needed for the LINCS team to understand how best to map and convert these datasets initiates a process of rethinking everything from research questions to publication of project results.

The second process of remediation occurs as researchers' datasets go through the LINCS workflow for conversion to LOD. Through ontology and vocabulary mappings, reconciliation against authorities and conversion to LOD, the LINCS team works both to understand the needs of individual researchers and to bring this understanding to aligning their data with our core ontology, CIDOC-CRM, or ways of extending the CIDOC base, to ensure compatibility across datasets and with LINCS tools. LINCS source datasets differ in form (structured, XML and natural language data) as well as in granularity, precision, domain, language, historical period, geopolitical location, and epistemology, in addition to researchers' own identities and disciplinary methodologies. Datasets therefore require quite generalized ontological structures that can accommodate these differences. The granular and nuanced complexities of human artifacts and human subjectivities, including the varied and interdependent, imbricated and intersectional (Crenshaw) facets of identity, given CIDOC's structure, manifest in vocabularies, which means that remediation of the data is being distributed across two different types of structure, which has implications for how the data can be used and accessed.

Finally, LINCS must create interfaces that mediate among these myriad perspectives and multiple worldviews, providing space for debates, difference, and contextualized and situated knowledge (Haraway) on the Semantic Web. As an infrastructure project funded to leverage as far as possible existing DH tools and platforms, LINCS has been challenged to make space for the desires of different research projects while adapting platforms to be usable by a broad audience and multiple projects. However, the technology stack is so complex that it is a challenge to make LOD usable for research, for reasons related to expertise, implementation, and infrastructure (Sanderson). Enabling users to make connections between data points across the Semantic Web is challenging, given the complexity of the data, meaning that the comfort of traditional media forms (images of paintings or print advertisements, for example) provides an important means of grounding the user within a novel and at times disorienting web interaction. We will demonstrate our attempts to overcome this complexity by showcasing how LINCS researchers are using LOD through two interfaces: the Context Browser plugin and our instance of ResearchSpace.